

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS THE INCREASED USE OF
SELF-MEDICATION AMONG NON-MEDICAL
UNDERGRADUATES WITH RESPECT TO FACTORS AND
COMMON DRUGS****Dr Mirza Mudasir Ali, Dr Muhammad Salman Shahid, Dr Muhammad Zubair
Nishtar Hospital Multan****Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Self-medication is application of medicines by a person on his own. Self-medication is used without the suggestion of any medical practitioner, on advice of common person or pharmacist. All around the world, the trend of self-medication is increasing. In Pakistan, the incidence of medication by a patient himself is in normal range.

Objectives: The objective of this research study was to check the incidence of self-medication and medicines that were frequently used by the non-medical students.

Subjects and Methods: This research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from May 2017 to September 2017. Questionnaire was designed that was completed by examiners.

Results: The results concluded that friends advise experience with similar symptoms (58%) and Pharmacists advise (28%) were common factor that contributed to self-medication. 71.2% was the incidence of self-medication.

Conclusion: Although most of the patients knew the harmful aspects of self-medication, but still in educated people, the incidence of self-medication is high.

Keywords: Self-medication, Prescription, Non-Medical students.

Corresponding author:

Aysha Jamil,
MO Indus Hospital

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Aysha Jamil et al., Insidious Sensorineural Hearing Loss In Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).**

INTRODUCTION:

Taking are using medicine without suggestion of an expert is referred as self-medication. Self-medication is either carried out for identification, method or observation of treatment. Obtaining medicine, suggesting previous methods to buy medicine, taking medicine already present in home and using each other's medicine with in a family is included in self-medication. [1] In third world countries, self-medication is mostly employed for management of disorder [2]. Medicine are easily available without any direction and that can be used without doctor's suggestion. This is the biggest reasons of use of self-medication on a large scale. Scarcity of doctors in back ward areas, promotion of medicines in a public medium via media [1], low standard of living high price of new medicines, and effect of parents may be included in those factors that contributed to self-medication [3] [4]. It is illustrated by other reports that poor health condition and death rates have been linked to common practice of self-medication [5], [6], [7]. The young generation has easy access to media. Media is promoting the drugs on a large scale that is harmful for youth. Misuse of medicine and wrong self-identification is increasing in young population day by day. So, among students, incorrect usage of medicines without any direction has become a complex issue. Among university student of Hong Kong, Karachi, Rio Grande, Brazil, the incidence of self-medications was reported to be 94%, 76% and 86.4% respectively. Illegal use of medicine information about drugs, old events with a similar medicine and science, considering the disease as mild were the frequently noticed factors connected with self-medication. [3] [4] [5] [8].

Like many developing nations in Pakistan too, medicines are easily available without any directions. As a result, common man become addicted to drugs. Unavailability of primary health services and high charges of doctors are the main factor that deals to self-medication. The objective of present research study was to check the incidence and to estimate the awareness of young generation related to self-medication. The study also aimed at the incidence of self-medication among non-medical students.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

This research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from May 2017 to September 2017. The sample size that was measured by using WHO

software determination of sample for health studies, was 73. But the sample size 94 was selected for this study. The level of confidence, precision and anticipated proportion were reported as 5%, 10% and 76% respectively.

Data collection procedure: A questionnaire was designed similar to the study health previously. 30 subjects were provided with this questionnaire. Problems in these questions were solved before its execution. Students behavior toward self-medication, demographic details, information of students and incidence of self-medication were recorded in the questionnaire. After explaining the aim of the study 94 volunteer students were selected for the study. VC of the university approved the study. Examiner themselves completed the proforma.

Data Analysis: the measurement regarding self-medication, causes, knowledge related to harmfulness of self-medications and various kinds of medicines was used, was made. For gender, simple frequencies were measured. Tables and figures were used for the illustration of these above mention factors. In order to check either these variables being measures were qualitative in nature or not, choice square was employed.

RESULTS:

The numbers of male and females selected for this study were 34 (36.2%) and 60 (63.8%) respectively. The age brackets of the participants were 22 years. 71.2% was the reported incidence of self-medication figure 1. Self-medication was being used by 39 (65%) out of 60. And 28 (82%) males out of 34. This dissimilarity noticed was not important. Pharmacists suggestion, friend's suggestions and old events with similar indications were the common factor observed in 28%, 15% and 58.2% cases respectively table 1. Anti-allergic, sleep inducers, pain killer and cough suppressants were the common medicines used by 25.5%, 23.4%, 63.8% and 42.5% students respectively figure 2. Harmful effect of self-medication is known by 76 (80.1%) students. In spite of this fact it is noticed that 33 (35.1%) students suggested self-medication to their fellows. 37 (39.4%) subjects out of 94 used medicines every time on the advice of doctor. Furthermore, the directed course of medicines was not completed by 50 (53.2%). It was observed that administration of prescribed drugs was changed by 43 subjects (45.7%) themselves.

Figure I: Proportion of students self-medicating, with gender distribution.

Figure II: common drugs used for self-medication

Table I: Factors that lead to self-medication among self-medicating students

Factor	Count	%age
Previous experience	39	58.2%
On pharmacist advice	19	28.3%
On friend's advice	10	15%

DISCUSSION:

In this study, the habit of self-medication was observed in 71.2% participants. The similar research studies were also conducted in Nigeria, Karachi, Brazil, Croatia and Hong Kong. The incidence of self-medication in these areas was found to be 53.8%, 76%, 86.4%, 88% and 94% respectively [3,4,5,6,9]. If results are compared with our study, it is observed that some areas have got low incidence some got high incidence. In a research study organized in Karachi, older event was the main factors that was associated with self-medication. For self-medication, awareness of a person was considered sufficient in Brazil [3, 4,

5]. Cough suppression and the pain killer were the main drugs used by the students in the current study. In the study organized in Hong Kong, older event and not giving any importance to suggestion of doctors were the main factors associated with self-medication. Chinese herbal medicines, analgesics, anti-allergic, anti-pyretic and topical preparation were the medicines, commonly used by the people of Hong Kong [3]. The people of Karachi were mostly using the anti-biotic, anti-pyretic and anti-analgesics [4]. It was observed that aspirin, acetaminophen dipyron, phytotherapeutic compounds and illegal drugs which includes LSD, Ecstasy, Cocaine and marijuana were commonly used medicine by the people of Brazil [5]. Anti-biotic and anti-malarials were the drugs used by the people of Nigeria for self-medication [9]. Besides the use of illegal drugs, the use of other medicines was similar in our study as shown in the above study. In Malaysia similar research study was organized. The incidence of counter (OTC) medications was found in 83.9% of the general public. Shortage of time reliably and easy approach were the main factors associated with self-medication. Awareness related to OTC medication in 82% of the participants was observed normal to low [7]. Vitamins and supplements along with sore throat products, pain killer and flu-cough medicines were commonly used OTC medicines. Among non-health care students of Sharjah University, UAE a similar study was organized. 59% of the students were reported with the habit of self-medication. Pharmacies was the main source of getting medicines for 49% of this student. Herbal store (3,2%), street market (13,7%) and relative are friends (4,2%) are the other means of getting self-medication. Normal health issue, high charges of doctors, minor illness, self-controlled as suggested by the doctors and getting fast relief were the common causes that lead to self-medication reported 33.5%, 33%, 38%, 45.5% and 67% cases respectively [8]. Current studies the incidence of self-medication is high. The students selected for this study belong to well-educated family. They now the threats of self-medication. The incidence of self-medication must be greater in illiterate group of society as their standard of living is low and cannot afford high charges of doctors also their knowledge related to self-medication is poor. Expect Brazil, where the use of illegal drug is common, the reasons reported by all other research study are almost comparable [5]. The habit of self-medication has many ill effects issues like drugs dependence and addictions, over and under dose age, complexities associated with these drugs that can lead to death and worldwide initiation of multi drugs

resistance pathogens are encouraged through the practice of self-medication [9,10].

CONCLUSION:

In spite of the fact that most of the people knew the threats of self-medication. Even though the incidence of self-medication in educated youth is high as illustrated in our study. In order to get rid of this issue the holistic approach is very necessary. This includes knowledge and information related to use of self-medication, availability of health care services to everyone, programs to avoid easy approach to non-prescribed drugs and tough rules related to pharmaceutical announcement.

REFERENCES:

1. Chang FR, Treivedi PK. Self-medication among university students of Karachi; prevalence, knowledge and attitude. 2007
2. Shankar PR, Partha P, Shenoy N. Self-medication and non-doctor prescription practices in Pokhara Valley, Western Nepal: A questionnaire-based study. *BMC Fam pract.* 2002; 3:17
3. Lau GS, Lee KK, Luk CT. Self-medication among university students in Hong Kong. *Asia Pac J Public Health.* 1995;8(3):153-7.
4. Zafar SN, Syed R, Waqar S, Zubairi AJ, Waqar T, Shaikh M, et al. Self-medication amongst university students of Karachi: prevalence, knowledge and attitudes. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2008 Apr;58(4):214-7
5. Marilia Garcez Correa da Silva, Maria Cristina Flores Soares, Ana Luiza Muccillo-Baisch. Self-medication among students. *BMC Public Health.* 2012; 12:339 doi:10.1186/1471-2458-12-339.